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A Traumatic Study of the Selected Short Stories of Jamil Jan Kochai's *The Haunting of Hajji Hotak and Other Stories*

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Abstract

This study focuses on trauma in Jamil Jan Kochai's collection of short stories, *The Haunting of Hajji Hotak and Other Stories*, from the theoretical perspective of Cathy Caruth. Attention will be paid to the following three stories *Return to Sender*, *Enough!* and *A Premonition; Recollected*. The research examines a number of traumatic experiences and their psychological effects on the characters from the perspective of Caruth's trauma theory. The study, based on the trauma theory as the theoretical framework, seeks to reveal the types of trauma and its effects on individual identities, relationships and societal dynamics within the context of Afghanistan. The study combines textual analysis and the qualitative research methodology to depict the cultural, historical and personal traumas described in the selected text. Through careful examination of the psychological and emotional effects of traumatic events on the characters, the research throws light on the complex nature of the human experience. The research applies the principles of traumatic witnessing, incomprehensibility, and belatedness from Caruth's theory in the analysis which makes the understanding of trauma representation in the selected literature richer. It focuses on the deep impact of traumatizing events on people and communities, and the role of stories in processing and understanding traumatic events.

Keywords: trauma, psychological impact, cultural trauma, traumatic witnessing, incomprehensibility and belatedness.

INTRODUCTION

The idea of incomprehensibility is the core element of Caruth's theory, which stresses the serious gap in traumatic memories. Trauma takes away the ability to comprehend and digest the experience in the person's life story. This cognitive inability isn't just a mere failure of comprehension but a core element of trauma that affects the way survivors experience their memories and relate to themselves. Caruth (1996) makes us see that traumatic events frequently are as if they happened to someone else, which results in a feeling of disconnection and alienation. This perceived otherness within oneself while being traumatized questions the very idea of identity and coherence of self, implying that the very core of trauma lies within its incomprehensibility.

The third story *A Premonition; Recollected* is about the character of Mor who tries to understand what happened to her during the war in conjunction with Caruth's view on delayed understanding and the nature of repetition of the trauma. The fragmented memories of Mor and the fact that she is trying to put together the pieces of her past experiences in order to create a coherent story, is a symbol of the temporal nature of traumatic memory. This story shows the theme of articulating with trauma, which is not a linear storytelling of all events but rather a random, repetitive series of flashes that must be reconciled and understood over time. Caruth's theoretical framework helps to understand the characters of Kochai with regard to the various aspects of trauma. The storytelling process of these narratives through the use of belatedness, traumatic witnessing, and delayed comprehension gives a panoramic and profound perception of the trauma experienced by the characters and communities in a conflict area (Kochai, 2022).

1.1 Research Objectives

The research objectives are

- To depict the various forms of trauma in Kochai's selected stories
- To examine the post-war circumstances in shaping the characters lives in Kochai's selected short stories within the framework of trauma theory

1.2 Significance of Study

This research holds great importance because it delves into the traumatic experiences of characters in war settings, drawing insights from Cathy Caruth's trauma theory outlined in her work *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History*. This study centres on the selected stories *Return to Sender*, *Enough!* and *A Premonition; Recollected*. This study aims at understanding how trauma is presented and dealt in Afghan culture. This research takes an interdisciplinary approach to the study of trauma narratives in Afghan literature in order to enhance understanding of the narrative's meaning for healing and resilience.

The research is specifically concerned with the lives of characters in the selected texts, and how the war has a drastic impact on

them. It examines the events and the devastating impacts of war on its adversaries, revealing the hardships and the challenges they face. This research not only helps to increase knowledge of trauma but it also gives new researchers the opportunity to look into the stresses that arise from war in the future.

Research Questions

The questions for study are

- What are the various forms of trauma depicted in Kochai's selected short stories?
- How do the post-war circumstances shape the character's lives in Kochai's selected short stories within the framework of trauma theory?

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

In addition, this theory has been increasingly seen as a multifaceted phenomenon that considers the effect of social and cultural aspects on how an individual perceives and responds to trauma. This is achieved by grasping the meaning and the impact of historical and intergenerational trauma among the marginalized peoples and how the societal structures contribute to and sustain the trauma. The creation of trauma informed care is a comprehensive approach to the treatment of trauma results as it focuses on the three aspects of the whole person (physical, psychological and emotional) and the total safety in all its service deliveries to help the survivors to regain their control and power.

Beyond the psychological and medical implications, trauma theory has become a prominent area of interest in the literary and cultural studies as well. Some scholars, for instance, Cathy Caruth and Dominick LaCapra, have made contributions in this field by investigating how trauma is represented in literature and media, and by considering the ethical issues of depicting traumatic events. The interdisciplinary application of trauma theory in the field shows a broadening of a scope which includes neural underpinnings of trauma, the effectiveness of particular therapeutic methods, and the importance of culturally competent care. As trauma theory constantly evolves, integrating the insights of psychology, neuroscience, sociology, anthropology and humanities, it highlights the intricacy of the subject and the necessity of multifaceted approaches to understanding and supporting human suffering and resilience.

Dori Laub has really made some important contributions to us understand and treat trauma, especially from his work with the Holocaust survivors. Laub found that when people speak about the most difficult things that have happened to them, the primary purpose isn't just to relieve the burden from themselves. It's the truth, and in a strange way, it's the most important part of the process. When a person recounts their traumatic event, it is as if they are re-living it all over again, but this time, they're able to overcome it in a way that helps them begin their healing process. This process needs another person to be empathetic and listen, that is to say, the other person needs to understand (Laub & Hamburger, 2017).

Laub and Hamburger (2017) stressed how the ability of the survivor to tell their story to someone is vital. However, the words are not the only important part of the whole story, but it's about the comprehension and recognition of the whole story. In this way, the person who has gone through the trauma knows that he or she is seen and believed, which is a big leap in the process of healing. Often, those who experienced trauma are in a hard position, as they know what happened, though they can hardly understand it and may not accept it at all. It feels like they are trying to part of them is to shield themselves from the pain by not fully grasping the trauma. Discussing the occurrence with someone will allow survivors to start to acknowledge their experiences more fully, which will help them to make sense of what had happened and how it affects their life now. In addition, Laub discussed in detail about the wider community and society which play a significant role in the healing process. The society may boost and speed up the healing process if it picks up and validates the trauma people have been through (like the Holocaust). However, if society denies those experiences or fails to acknowledge that they ever happened, it can make a situation completely unbearable for survivors. Laub's work is incredibly important in that it tells us that the process of overcoming trauma isn't just about an individual working through their experience. It is as much about how their story is heard, comprehended, and accepted as it is about them. It is a noticeable fact that this demonstrates how it is possible to just be there for someone and to listen, and to acknowledge that they are in pain (Laub & Hamburger, 2017).

As to the question of the social-political dimension of the society, the traumatology with its basic concepts and ideas by Allan Feldman, an anthropologist and ethnographer, allows us to get a good idea of how trauma affects this dimension. The body, blood and guts, sensory experience, and politics of cultural memory are the main topics that he discusses. His works, in specific, remove the gap in trauma research by opening the eyes on the complexities of the connection between trauma narratives and social and political patterns (Feldman, 1990).

Caruth (2013) in her work does not only prove the ethical demand to be with the survivors of trauma but rather to listen to their stories as well. This is a motive to think about the miseries of other people. This ethical approach is also marked by recognizing trauma as a call for responsibility which is in turn an activity that is moving beyond an acknowledgement of the trauma but is instead an actual engagement with the narrative of trauma. It is through involvement in the process of recovering that people can start to discover the ways they can make sense of their experiences and help the society that has been affected by trauma. Caruth's contribution to the field of trauma studies has profoundly affected it, triggering a lot of great works of literary criticism, psychology, psychoanalysis, cultural studies, and history. Her research has not only bridged the gaps in the understanding of trauma mechanisms, the role of narrative in traumatic experience processing, and the ethics of trauma witnessing and responding to trauma. Caruth's cross-disciplinary work has done a lot for the discourse on trauma, memory, and identity, giving us deeper understanding of human hardship and strength (Caruth, 2013).

Though this is an area where most people agree with Van der Kolk, some opponents still have different opinions regarding his strong support for alternative therapies such as EMDR and yoga. The critics maintain the view that more clinical tests are required to accept such treatments as universally applicable for trauma. On the other hand, the interdisciplinary approach which

Van der Kolk followed has left a significant mark on trauma therapy as well as mental health treatment, thus, making possible the use of a broad range of therapeutic practices which are aimed at comprehensively addressing the needs of trauma survivors (KolK, 2014).

The book of *Trauma and Recovery* approaches trauma as a multifaceted phenomenon, which involves the historical sources of trauma, its clinical aspects, and the individual and collective path of recovery. Herman's work is considered as a starting point for the trauma psychology and therapy, providing the fundamental knowledge of the long-term consequences of the physical violence and the recovery routes that apply not only to the individuals but also to the communities they belong to (Herman, 1992).

In his book *The Trauma Question*, Luckhurst (2008) conducts a detailed analysis of trauma, which involves looking into its historical origins, cultural implications and individual and communal identities. Through his narrative, Luckhurst examines the historical background of the word trauma, which comes from the medical world of the 19th century when it was used to describe only physical wounds. The change of the understanding of trauma from physical injuries to psychological phenomena is described including the fact that the definition enlarged from the perception of the trauma as something that caused physical injuries to the one that was caused by shocking and stressful experiences.

The author goes on to talk about the accreditation of PTSD in 1980 by the American Psychiatric Association, the moment which turned out to be crucial for the trauma paradigm. Luckhurst examines the expansion of the PTSD diagnosis from its early application to direct personal violence, to cover the experiences of people witnessing atrocities or learning about trauma inflicted on the close associates. A substantial part of the book is dedicated to the portrayal of trauma in different cultural formats such as literature, film, and art. Luckhurst investigates the different ways in which trauma has been conveyed in stories and images. He analyzes books from the likes of Toni Morrison and movies from David Lynch. He talked about the function of the story in the traumatic experience processing, and the way in which the cultural works can use and reflect the social understandings of trauma (Luckhurst, 2008).

This narration process is not only an individual healing way but also it turns out to be a way of protecting the communal shared past. Through the novels of Toni Morrison we get an insightful exploration of trauma and its consequences especially among the African Americans. Through her work she brings attention to the intricacy of trauma which is often associated with racial and historical injustices and the power of community and expressing through narratives to overcome this. Through her wise depiction of these ideas, Morrison gives us a chance of looking at the concept of healing and the human potential of resilience. This literature review emphasizes the need for the consideration and understanding of trauma as presented in Morrison's novels. It shows that the powerful potential of healing embedded in the processes of community support and storytelling could be transformative. She does it by creating a very colorful world and showing us thematic depth; thus, she does not only shine the light on the scars of the past traumas, but also shows us the ways to heal and to rebuild (Garima, 2019). Trauma in Ishiguro's novels is inextricably connected to memory and narrative, in which the traumatized characters experience difficulties in recognizing their past and present as a coherent and continuous process (Li, 2019).

In her dissertation, Li (2019) explains how Ishiguro uses such narrative devices as disjointed narration, the untrustworthy narrator, and the blending of personal and historical narratives to mirror the disjointed and inaccessible nature of traumatic memory. These narrative stratagems not only shows the inner struggles of the characters but also invites readers to be active as they keep on guessing the story, similar to the process of working through trauma.

The thesis provides findings which show that Ishiguro's narrative techniques are effective in portraying the complexity of trauma, and it is through this that the audience can observe how individuals deal with their past, the reconstruction of identity, and the search for healing. Ishiguro's novels clearly alert us to the fact that narration is a vital tool that helps us to cope with unbearable painful situations and can make reconciliation possible. The novels also bring up the topics of how individuals are affected by historical events and societal changes and they make it clear that the author's main concern is the human condition in different cultures and periods of history (Li, 2021).

In *Exploration of Trauma Narrative in The Kite Runner* by Yang Chun, the researcher investigates how Khaled Hosseini presents trauma in the book *The Kite Runner*. This article provides a thorough analysis by interrelating the novel's treatment of personal and collective trauma with the wider social-historic perspective of Afghanistan. Through trauma theory and with close reading of the text, Yang's objective is to unveil the intricate web of trauma that the characters, and - most importantly - Amir, are going through, as well as that of the Afghan society. The foundation of Yang's analysis falls on the theory of trauma, where she quoted from Freud, Caruth, Whitehead, and Erikson to distinguish between individual and collective traumas (Chun, 2014).

Chun (2017) highlights how Hosseini uses the life's story of Amir who complements the national pain of Afghanistan in order to demonstrate multiple dimensions of trauma, involving sins, guilt, salvation, racial issues, and national tragedy. The paper describes Hosseini as a writer who uses the narrative to represent the trauma as opposed to simply describing it, which agrees with Anne Whitehead's argument that trauma fiction has the capability to shift the relationship between language and experience. As far as methodology, she utilizes a qualitative approach via a precise text analysis of *The Kite Runner*, mainly investigating the way traumatic experiences are telling and how they affect the characters' mental state and behavior. Through depiction of instances of trauma that Amir and other characters face, Yang shows how Salaam feels not only personal pain but also represent the whole Afghanistan's community suffering due to historical atrocities and ongoing conflicts.

The dissertation of Buczynski (2016) constitutes a significant contribution to the Trauma Studies and Literary Analysis by pointing out the way metaphor acts as the bridge between the unspeakable nature of trauma and the necessity of expressing and understanding the traumatic experiences. The study of various cultural settings and literary traditions emphasizes the common dimension of trauma, and the artistic methods that authors resorted to, to portray the human suffering's depth and complexity (Buczynski, 2016).

InayatUllah (2020) discusses in his article *War Memory, Psychological Trauma, and Literary Witnessing: A closer look at the lively dialog between works of literature* and the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan from 1979 to 1989, which made a profound historical and

psychological impact on the country, is taken in the article *Afghan Cultural Production in Focus*. InayatUllah, by a thorough analysis of Atiq Rahimi's novel *Earth and Ashes*, studies how Afghan Anglophone fiction is, indeed, the key channel for the voicing and preservation of collective memory and trauma that the Afghan people have experienced throughout this turbulent period.

Through underlining the potential of literary works to document and work through the traumas, the article stands to reveal the power of storytelling in the process of healing and memorializing the scars created by conflict (InayatUllah, 2020).

The result of the study that Hemingway's characters go through a transformation as a result of their war experiences that change the way they see life and themselves. Symbolically, Barnes, a usual person who also suffered from both physical and as well as psychological injuries that made him impotent and disillusioned is also a living metaphor to that. The narrative reveals the characters' search for the transitory pleasures and relationships in a bid to escape or come to terms with their pain, but in a futile attempt (Sattari and Tawhidyar, 2020).

In the article titled *Dispersal of Time and Trauma in Postmodern Novel: Slaughterhouse- Five* Kalecik (2023) explores the complex portrayal of trauma and time in Kurt Vonnegut's novel *Slaughterhouse-Five*. This research particularly deals with how the postmodern narrative structure of the novel mirrors the disjointed and non-chronological experience of the PTSD. The central theme of the novel, which is the protagonist Billy Pilgrim's disturbed conception of time because of his experiences in World War II, is explored.

Kalecik (2023) employed the technique of text analysis and this allows the writer to look into the narrative strategies Vonnegut uses to depict trauma. The treatment of the subjects, such as the disorder of temporal sequence, the fission of memory, and the non-linear development of the main character's life history, that is similar with the lasting psychological effect of trauma, is also included. The outcomes of the research indicate that Vonnegut refers to postmodernism as a way of criticizing conventional narrative ways and of asking about reality and memory in the context of trauma. The novel's narrative structure, which is fragmented, is a metaphor for the lives torn apart by trauma and it symbolizes the difficulties such survivors face in trying to make sense of their traumatic experiences and reintegrating into society. The book, using the character of Billy Pilgrim, illustrates that the effect of war is everlasting and that the sense of displacement and feeling of being foreign can continue even after the war ends.

To sum up, this paper is a part of the context that introduces the use of modern literature to explore and articulate diverse mental states such as trauma, particularly noting the peculiar narrative structures that confuse the conventional storytelling to adequately represent the hectic and fragmented nature of traumatic memory (Kalecik, 2023).

Khan and Tabbasum (2022) published The article titled *War Memories and Peacebuilding in From East Pakistan to Bangladesh* in the *Journal of Communication and Cultural Trends* considers the employing of memoirs for peacebuilding whereby individuals recount their traumatic experiences to produce narratives that may lead to reconciliation and understanding. The researcher utilizes Saadullah Khan's memoirs which are a firsthand account and a witness to events during the Bangladesh Liberation War of 1971 as a primary case study. The texts by her are examined through the DTT theory, which is offered by Michael Rothberg and is the tool for understanding how narratives can break the cycles of violence and help the process of healing and peace.

The methodology that is chosen is qualitative which involves critical textual analysis of Khan's memoirs to investigate the depiction of war memories and the significance of their place in peacebuilding processes. On the other hand, the emphasis is on the fact that these memories, expressed using narratives, can aid individuals and societies in passing through the conflicts and to a greater empathy and understanding of the former enemies.

Results of the study reveal that the memoir by Khan does not glorify war but explains the war in a balanced manner taking all the complexities and human cost of the conflict into account. Through the humanization of both sides and the avoidance of any kind of enemy demonization, Khan's storyline opens up the chance of reconciliation. His stories overturn the common beliefs of war, which are often the basis for conflicts and the perpetuation of war, and instead focus on the humanity of persons, the fight for survival, and the compassion that exist in relationships across divides. This article belongs to the studies on trauma and narration which

provide evidence for the impact of the memories of war on the personal and collective level and the way they are reflected in the literature that not only describes historical events but also plays a significant role in the process of healing and reconciliation (Tabbasum, 2022).

Fontana and Rosenheck (1999) write an article of *A Model of War Zone Stressors and Posttraumatic Stress Disorder* which offers a theoretical model to investigate the connection between different war zone stressors and the emergence of Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) in veterans. This model takes the multi-factorial approach into account, which covers not only the exposure to combat but also the witnessing of death and injury, the threat of personal harm, the possibility of being involved in atrocities, and the physical environmental conditions like a lack of resources. It is the data from the National Vietnam Veterans Readjustment Study that is used in this research, structural equation modelling is employed to test the proposed paths and to validate the relationships among these variables.

The main message of the speech is investigative and descriptive. It is supported by the author's professional background along with the fact that he has a deep understanding of the subject matter concerning health and human rights. In this process, readers experience a detailed, deep examination of issues associated with post-war situations. By giving medicine, anthropology, public health, and human rights law as the areas of multidisciplinary approach, post-trauma dialogue goes beyond the ecological and social dimensions.

The writing of the article is done by a methodology that uses the analytical and narrative style of the author who is a well-known person in the health and human rights field. This makes the realities of war trauma be well explained. The multi-disciplinary approach that LHH uses, which integrates medicine, anthropology, public health, and human rights law into one holistic framework is designed to widen the conversation about trauma to include ecological and societal dimensions.

Leaning (2021) highlights several critical insights: the shortcomings of the international humanitarian law in providing safety

of the civilians, the changes of local ecologies into wastelands by war, and the dissipation of personal and communal identify because of the breakdown of social and moral structures. She argues that the rules of engagement that in the past had facilitated the preservation of the distinction between combatants and non-combatants have been now eroded, leaving civilians in a continuous state of insecurity and threatening their psychological well-being as well as the social structure.

Modern wars, including internal and intrastate conflicts, continue to have a devastating effect on civilians through the physical, psychological, and social damages they inflict. The consequences of these are not usually taken into account by the existing legal frameworks and humanitarian assistance. In his view, trauma is not only the direct impact of violence on the human body but also involves ecological damage, social disintegration, and the deep sense of loneliness experienced by people in war situations (Leaning, 2021).

An article by Amrita Rathi, titled *Psychological Impact of Victims of War and Conflict*, studies the intricate psychological and emotional effects that war has on civilian non-combatants, such as children, women, and senior citizens. Rathi's work is based in Teachers College, Columbia University, and is divided into the two main types of impact of war, namely, the direct impact of PTSD, depression, anxiety, loss of family members, economic hardships, and displacement and the indirect impact. Through her studies, she tries to pinpoint the specifics of emotional recovery and resilience of these vulnerable groups negatively impacted by war (Rathi, 2019)

Rathi (2019) applies a mixed methodology to understand how normal people develop psychological resilience and psychopathology in war-torn areas. This will entail analyzing empirical studies, theories, and frameworks on trauma and resilience written by such authors as Elbedour, Benseel, Bastien, Bonanno, Galea, Bucciarelli, Vlahov, and others.

Kochai's achievement is highly appreciated for his ironic analysis of modern American life and his demonstration of the spiritual and folklore traditions of Afghanistan. His stories tend to cross the boundaries of ordinary and bring the reader to the brink of the perception of reality, presenting a deep analysis of the nature of traumatic events and complicated historical narratives. This body of work is an important contribution to modern literature about war and its aftermath, particularly in the context of Afghanistan. It does provide a profound perspective of individual and political consequences of conflict, therefore it makes it a good subject to consider when we are talking about how war is experienced and remembered by its main participants (Noor, 2023).

These characters in different stories, either dead or alive serve as the other part of the memory gaps and the present. The anthology is a task for the reader who tries to fill the gaps, a feeling like the one refugees experience when they want to find their place and create their own meanings (Mayer, 2022).

Research Gap

The study is new on the selected text as there is little work regarding trauma done on the text before. The study will apply trauma theory of Cathy Caruth from her work *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History* on the characters Amina, Yusuf, Rangeena and Mor who are war victims and the long-lasting impacts of war on their minds and bodies. The literature review reflects the shortcomings of the shortage of reviewed work from the same author because very few literary research was available. The selected text is written in 2023 and there is minute details available about it in the form of journals and articles. Although the growing number literature on trauma theory and its application in literary works, there is a wide gap in study, which explains how the precise narratives in these stories by Jamil Jan Kochai interact with trauma in a unique way, focusing on the nuances of unclaimed experiences and trauma occurring within the context of Afghan and refugee society in the United States. Therefore, a comprehensive study of the details of trauma described in these stories, how to remember, communicate, and how to shape the cultural identity and commitment of Afghan immigrants and their problems, provides a more ambiguous and culturally sensitive perspective for applying the theory of trauma to these stories. This study will help gain a profounder understanding of the difficulties of traumatic narrative in immigrant and refugee literature and provide insight into how these stories serve different purposes for the study of trauma and memory. This study will help gain a profounder understanding of the difficulties of traumatic narrative in immigrant and refugee literature and provide insight into how these stories serve different purposes for the study of trauma and memory.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The qualitative method is applied in the study. The theory of Trauma will serve as the theoretical basis. These three stories are the source of our data. The main data source is the text of these short stories. The primary data is the text of the short stories that illustrate elements of trauma like the trauma of loss, physical and mental sufferings of other characters as a result of war and the characters' reaction and the effect of war on their lives. The experience of war in the selected text is not artistic but it is associated with true war events in Afghanistan during the Soviet Invasion. The secondary source of data are research articles, journals, and books related to theories. The secondary data is the concept of trauma presented by Cathy Caruth. However, she discusses some of the aspects of trauma that are derived from Sigmund Freud's concept of trauma in her book *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma Narrative and History*; but this research will be restricted to Caruth's concepts of belatedness, incomprehensibility and traumatic witnessing.

This study makes use of a textual analysis in conjunction with a thematic exploration of the application of Cathy Caruth's trauma theory. Textual analysis is a process of close reading of the targeted stories in order to identify the incidents of trauma and analyze how they are presented in the narration. The interpretation process is a deep reading and analysis of the text which is aimed at discovering the hidden themes, symbols and motifs that are associated with traumatic events. Thematic issues are used to demonstrate how trauma is portrayed and presented in the stories. Themes of war, loss, and disruption of experience are shown in the stories to explore the deepest psychological and emotional layers of the trauma.

The study is based on the full comprehension of how trauma theory, especially Caruth's theory, is used in literature by combining textual analysis with thematic exploration. The methodology of the study aims to show the complex interplay

between the traumatic experiences and storytelling, which would in turn demonstrate the psychological effects of trauma for both individuals and society.

TEXTUAL ANALYSIS

Types of Trauma in Selected Stories

The chosen stories contain different kinds of experiences, which the characters suffer from. They confront the hardships such as the trauma which has been passed down from generation to generation, mental pain and being forced to migrate from their home. These traumatic events are the core of the character's personalities and lives. As the stories progress, we observe how the characters' pasts intertwine with each other, making it really difficult for them to reach their goals of healing and peace.

War Trauma

War trauma, commonly denoted as combat trauma or combat stress, embodies the psychological and emotional injuries caused by the experience of the horrors of war and conflict. It covers a broad variety of lifelong experiences, such as seeing or taking part in violence, the loss of friends or relatives, injuries, displacement, and the constant danger to one's life. The war aftermath can take different forms, including PTSD, depression, anxiety, survivor's guilt, and other mental health issues. It touches people and their families, and communities in a deep way, creating pain that can be felt years after the conflict is over, affecting relationships, functioning and well-being in general.

In *Return to Sender* in the book by Jamil Jan Kochai, war trauma is a recurring theme which is portrayed through the characters' experiences in the Afghanistan country during the war. The first paragraph of the story is very complicated and profound, describing Dr. Yusuf Ibrahim's internal conflicts with the traumas of war and his family legacy. The image of his father's beard haunts him, and it is a reminder of cultural expectations and the ever-present memories of past trauma. Yusuf's day-to-day battle with the ghost of his father's beard symbolizes both internal and external battles he is fighting on a daily basis, which in its turn shows the bigger problem of surviving in a war-torn country. The narrative emphasizes family and cultural legacy, showing that Yusuf's struggle is not only his own but also that of Afghanistan, which has been a country at war for many years (Kochai, 2022).

In the story the motif of receiving dismembered limbs in anonymous packages is a powerful metaphor of the loss and devastation war trauma causes. Amina's heart wrenching story of discovering Ismael's dismembered body parts, depicts the physical, emotional, and psychological damage of conflict on individuals and their families. The careful assemblage and sorting out of Ismael's body parts by Amina epitomize the frantic efforts to restore completeness and to make sense out of a senseless violence. In Amina's efforts to make Ismael whole again by sewing him back together, the story represents man's ability to find healing when he is torn apart by war.

In *Enough!* War trauma is shown through the character of Rangeena, who fights extremely with the deep grief and pain of losing her son Watak to war. The repetition of enough in her inner voice shows that her breaking point has been reached, and this is also an expression of the exhaustion from the whole weight of pain and violence. As Rangeena's case demonstrates, the individual and collective trauma of war does not just end with the end of conflicts but continues to shape the identities and relationships of those who have experienced the war. The story explores the multi-layered character of mourning and how war trauma can affect not only individuals but the whole community as well.

In *A Premonition; Recollected*, the war trauma is represented by Mor's flashback or repressed memory of the time when her brothers have been killed by the gunmen in the snow. The plot is able to make the gunmen war victims through showing their own suffering and loss along with the disorientation of war. Mor's contemplation over the physical and emotional aspects of their life reveals the complex nature of empathy and trauma. The story illustrates the tragedy of those who are not soldiers who lose their lives and the psychological damage that is passed on for generations, showing the deep and long term effects it has on people and communities.

Trauma of Loss and Mourning

The experience of losing someone and mourning the loss is a very deep and universal one that is not limited by cultural or geographical boundaries. It is the experience of the deep sorrow and despair that comes with the death or loss of loved ones, making people struggle with deep emotional pain and confusing philosophical questions. When you have lost someone close to you, whether it is a family member, friend or even a community member, the trauma of loss and mourning is with you all the time, affecting the way you see the world, your relationships and perspectives.

The Trauma of Loss and Grief in the story *Return to Sender* Amina's job as a paediatrician in war-torn country puts her at the epicentre of the human cost of war, seeing first-hand the most horrific of its consequences. The narrative evocatively reflects the emotional and psychological strain this exposure triggers for healthcare workers who, despite their professional duties, are not free from the trauma of loss and grief. The months Amina spends at the hospital, assisting in surgeries and watching kids dying, transform her, and the boundary between her professional and personal life dissolves and the way she perceives her own son Ismail changes.

The text describes Amina's harrowing experiences, "Amina was a paediatrician before the war, but in the past six months she has performed amputations, cauterizations, two illegal vasectomies and a secret assisted suicide even her husband was not aware of." (Kochai, 2022,

p. 20). This part of the story shows the extremity of the actions Amina has to take, going beyond her training due to the dire circumstances of the war. Her behavior, arising from the necessity, highlights the versatility and resilience of healthcare workers in crisis situations, however, it also suggests the burden on their shoulders and ethical dilemmas that they may face.

Her encounters with casualties of war deeply affected her. "She had seen patients walk into her hospital without any assistance, carrying with them the wreckage of their own torn limbs" (Kochai, 2022, p. 20). This not only reveals the physical destruction

but also serves as a metaphor for the psychological wreckage that Amina, and others in her position, must overcome. The unceasing stream of the wounded and dead patients, including children, symbolizes the senseless cruelty of war and its devastating consequences to the innocent.

The story captures the emotional toll on Amina through her interaction with the children in her care “In fact, so many children had died under her care or in her very hands their eyes, their eyelashes staring up into her life on the edge of death and then no longer the edge but in the heart of the Thing itself that they had begun to alter the way she looked upon her only son Ismael” (Kochai, 2022, p. 20). This passage shows how the continuous effects of death and suffering start to affect Amina’s view of her own child, proving the deep-seated trauma that can go through the most sacred and personal part of a person’s life.

The loss and grief that the main character and his family in *Return to Sender* undergo in the wake of their father’s death is a theme that runs consistently throughout the story and wreaks havoc and pain on them. The author presents the character of Yusuf who shows the experience of grief and the development of personal identity and relationships while under the influence of the war in Afghanistan. The loss of the father is the main reason why the main character suffers from trauma. The depth of his sorrow is apparent and he shows the audience a great range of emotions from rage to confusion and extreme sadness and longing. The author provides a very good illustration of the inner turmoil of the protagonist who has a hard time in accepting the fact that his father is no longer in his life as he is showing the physical sensation and the disorientation that is caused by such an event.

Cultural and generational trauma

The journey of Yusuf’s life and his home to Afghanistan is very much a load of cultural and generational trauma. With Amina and he back to Afghanistan to help rebuild their country, Yusuf faces the same torment he was fleeing. The narrative is centered around the hospital that the characters work at, which is a microcosm of the wide-ranging effects of the war on Afghan society, displaying the endless cycle of violence and the toll it takes on the healthcare professionals and the civilian population. The description of Amina’s work and its psychological impact on her: “The last six months of their stay in Kabul had been like the entire local hospital had been placed on their shoulders alone” (Kochai, 2022, p. 20). This not only represents the physical and psychological burden carried by Yusuf and Amina but also reveals the broader societal trauma of a country that is constantly bleeding from the conflict. Thus, they are addressing the cultural and generational trauma that is deeply rooted in Afghan society through their service of healing.

Moreover, the story illustrates the impact of the war on the long-term through Amina’s professional and personal life. Her engagement with wounded and dying children and her subsequent concerns for her own son’s well-being demonstrate how trauma goes beyond individual experiences, affecting parental fear and family dynamics. Yusuf is another one who is faced with this, his decision to go back to Afghanistan and his experiences there coincide with the broader narrative many Afghans who have lived through decades of conflict. This joint experience of defiance, resilience, and hope in the face of despair is the true essence of cultural and generational trauma a collective memory of pain and survival which determines the national identity and influences individual lives.

The *Kite Runner* by Khaled Hosseini is a story in which cultural trauma is a common theme and is closely linked to the difficult past of Afghanistan. The story occurs against the background of the Soviet invasion, a disastrous event that destroys the peace and harmony of Afghan society, resulting in displacement, violence and degradation of traditional values. The class and ethnic divisions, especially the Hazard discrimination, emphasize the societal cracks which are the main reason for the cultural trauma. The way Amir betrays Hassan at the kite-fighting tournament becomes a powerful metaphor, not only representing Amir’s personal guilt but also the larger betrayal of cultural values and trust in the Afghan community.

The movement of characters such as Amir and Baba can be compared to the wider exodus of Afghan people who are fleeing the horrors of war, thus adding to the cultural trauma through the loss of homeland and identity. The Taliban rule which has followed is another blow, with the strict regime limiting personal freedoms and erasing Afghanistan’s cultural heritage. The transgenerational effect is obviously manifested in the case of Sohrab, Hassan’s son, who has both physical and emotional scars of the previous generation’s suffering, indicating the long-lasting nature of cultural trauma. Throughout the plot the writer takes the reader on a journey that shows how historical events and individual choices are inextricably linked in shaping individual destinies and the national identity of a people who are struggling with the indelible scars of the past (Hosseini, 2003).

Intergenerational trauma in *Enough!* is expressed perfectly by the character of Rangeena and her relationship with her son. Such a type of trauma refers to the fact that the consequences of the traumatic experiences are not only borne by those who directly experience them but can be passed down from one generation to the next within the family. Rangeena, who has been through Soviet invasion of Afghanistan, is still carrying the heavy burden of her past experiences, including the death of her brother Watak and the deep changes that war has brought into her life. These events mold her point of view, her fears, and her relations with family members, especially her son who is haunted by the unresolved traumas that are the shadow of his childhood.

The plot of the story portrays Rangeena’s inner psychological and emotional conflict, exemplified by her refusal to take medicine for “anxiety,” “mania,” and “panic,” which clearly shows her ongoing struggle against mental health problems resulting from her traumatizing experiences. As it is described in the story, “Rangeena has inadvertently lost the pills he says are for her heart but which in fact Rangeena found out were for her mind picking up on the words ‘anxiety’ and ‘mania’ and ‘panic’ (Kochai, 2022, p. 34). Rangeena’s son, who shows his anger and misinterpretations towards his mother, is an example of the second impact of her trauma. The way he behaves is a mirror of his inherited grief and unresolved conflict, which is proof of how the trauma from the past is affecting his actions and his relationship with Rangeena. This is a manifestation of intergenerational trauma, where the effects of the initial trauma spread outward to the rest of the generation.

Moreover, Rangeena’s reflections on her life and the symbolic representation of her carrying the trauma. The lines from the text Rangeena’s withered lungs hadn’t been ceaselessly aching since the night her body absorbed so much smoke and debris

from Soviet cluster bombs" (Kochai, 2022, p. 35) emphasize the impact of her experiences throughout the story. The story shows how she is the product of her personal history of loss, displacement, and war that has made her who she is as well as greatly influenced her family.

A Premonition; Recollected which is a masterful story that describes the cyclic nature of violence and distress, portraying the intergenerational trauma of a family that was impacted by the Afghan conflict. The story is about two gunmen who are laying in wait, and on the other side is Mor who will remember this vision years later, and this will represent how her family's past is connected to the broader history of violence in Afghanistan. Intergenerational trauma, as displayed in this story, is the passing on of the trauma experienced by one generation to the next generations. This type of trauma is not only affecting those who directly experienced the traumatic event, but it is also deeply impacting their descendants, as the family history is shaped, behaviour patterns are changed, and the worldview of the descendants is influenced.

Physical trauma

The story *Enough!*, is very descriptive as it talks about the physical pain that the character Rangeena went through and her recollections of the past. This suffering in the narrative shows a reflection of the brutal reality of life in Afghanistan where war, loss, and the physical consequences of these experiences on the body are the norm. One of the most obvious physical effects mentioned is Rangeena's encounter with a bomb blast after she says that "Since the night her body absorbed so much smoke and debris from Soviet cluster bombs she had ash leaking out of her nose and ears" (Kochai, 2022, p. 35). This line fully portrays the immediate physical effect of war on the human body, emphasizing the visible, painful traces of conflict that Rangeena carries with her.

Furthermore, the plot takes Rangeena's chronic health problems, worsened by the stress and post-traumatic stress disorder, into consideration. Her dependence on an oxygen tank for the purpose of breathing, her "withered lungs" and the physical pains she undergoes highlight the long term implication of her experiences. These physical ailments are not only signs of her past but also every day hurdles that affect the quality of her life. Furthermore, the story also incorporates the theme of physical harm and violence faced in conflicts as Rangeena recalls "her children picking apples while searching for her eldest son who thank Allah (all Praise Be To Him) was not eaten by those dogs or blown to pieces by the bombs or shot near the bank of a stream" (Kochai, 2022, p. 38). It brings out the ever-present danger of physical violence that dominates the lives of those who reside in war-stricken regions, ultimately emphasizing the constant fear of losing loved ones to violence.

The story *Return to Sender* contains physical injury as a result of the bomb blast that occurred in an accident. The story, has a deep influence on Yousaf's physical and mental health, which reminds him of the prevalence of danger and violence in Afghanistan. Yousaf's physical injuries are portrayed in great details and vividness to show you how much pain he was suffering. Yousaf's struggle to deal with the limitations and pain of his injuries, as well as the hurdles he encounters in getting proper medical care and support in a country that is in conflict and is unstable, is narrated by Kochai.

The main character of the story, Yousaf's physical injury serves as the plot device through which Kochai looks at the broader theme of survival and resilience against all odds. The physical injury of Yousaf is a strong indicator that the war in Afghanistan does not differentiate between anyone as the destructive nature of war is now fully evident. In Yousaf's story, the character's struggle with his own losses and exile, is an intensely bitter reflection of the human cost of war and this makes one to think about the wide implications of political conflicts.

Psychological and emotional trauma

The story *Return to Sender* deals with emotional trauma by delving into the intersecting lives of the characters, especially into the intricate emotions of the protagonist's relationship with his family and the people he encounters as he tries to discover the last vestiges of his brother's life. In the story, the author employs symbolism, significant details, and the exploration of the emotional wounds of war, loss, and the preservation of familial ties in the face of such hardships to delve into the dark side of war. There is no doubt that one area of emotional trauma in this story

is when Yusuf encounters the parcels delivered to his door, which contain the pieces of his son's body. undefined "He nearly sprinted out of his building into the parking lot of his complex where his neighbors were all abustle with a hundred different tasks, one of which he knew was related to the delivery of the package he carried in his hands" (Kochai, 2022, p. 23).

This is a moment when the personal tragedy is intertwined with the everyday routine of the neighbours and it demonstrates how isolated the protagonist is in his grief which is beyond the comprehension of the people around him. In a similar way, the story explores the mother's experience of trauma by her communication with the other package. undefined "But as Amina turned to leave the kitchen to check on Ismael, she happened to glance very quickly in the direction of the cardboard box, nestled between the Camus and the chai, which at that exact moment almost seemed to shudder" (Kochai, 2022, p. 22). This instant shows the true extent of her emotional pain and her effort to keep the hope alive in conditions that are beyond human imagination.

The story also focuses on the broader effect of trauma as a family grieves over the loss of their son. The intricate process of rejoining his body parts, delivered to their home, becomes a symbol for the endeavor to glue together a life that shattered in the wake of violence. The parents' efforts to sew their son back together, even though it is physically impossible, accentuate the devastating effects of trauma on the family, pointing to their aspirations to have their son whole again and return to their previous lives in the midst of the havoc.

In *Enough!* psychological and emotional damage is best exemplified in the heart-wrenching journey of war and its consequences on her private life and family members. The narrative penetrates to the very depths of war scars, loss, and the struggle to resist the onslaught of adversity by maintaining identity and family. The representation of Rangeena's psychological trauma is very evocative through her memories and her present family condition. The story talks about how the war experience and loss have seeped into her very soul, and thus she is no longer able to relate to her son and grandchildren with the same degree of

closeness she did before.

The mentioning of Rangeena's past, including the loss of loved ones and the impact of war, highlights the psychological toll these events have taken on her: Rangeena is astonished by the question as to how long she has to sit and perish entirely due to the antagonism of her family members..." (Kochai, 2022, p. 39). This sentence presents a picture of the internal war in Rangeena's mind; she is trying to fight the psychological influence of her torture history while she deals with the family tensions. Rangeena's emotional trauma is also portrayed through her feelings of aloneness, not being understood, and her thoughts about the past and present. The story is her psychological burden, especially her relationship with her son, who does not understand her and her past experiences.

Post war Circumstances in shaping characters lives

In *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History*, Cathy Caruth gives a profound exploration of the effects of post-war condition on the lives of victims, particularly highlighting the complicated and sometimes delayed appearances of trauma. She investigates the complexity of the manner individuals deal with and experience the aftermath of war as well as the unexpected ways in which trauma comes to the surface. Caruth's method is defined by a skillful fusion of psychoanalytic theory and literary analysis, which shows the way how traumatic events resonate and mold the lives of victims months and years after the conflict has ended. She emphasizes trauma as a phenomenon that is not entirely understood or processed immediately after its occurrence, this is why it reappears in unforeseen forms like flashbacks, dreams, or intrusive memories. The most intriguing thing of this point of view is the lasting, sometimes terrifying, effect of war on the lives of survivors, making them rethink their identity, memory and the way they look at the environment.

The story of Jamil Jan Kochai in his book *The Haunting of Hajji Hotak and Other Stories* portrays trauma through Cathy Caruth's theories. Caruth's work, notably in *Unclaimed Experience: Trauma, Narrative, and History*, that show indirect experience of trauma through stories, dreams or behaviors instead of direct recall, is a topic of the book. Hence, the indirect experience in the story is in line with the narrative structure and thematic concerns of *Return to Sender*, where the horrors of war and the layers of personal and collective trauma are portrayed through a narrative that combines the real with the surreal, and the personal with the political.

In A Premonition; Recollected

Cathy Caruth's trauma theory is dedicated to the psychological dimension of traumatic experiences and how these experiences are experienced, remembered and re-lived by people. The narration of Mor which she was talking about her brothers' death is in line with Caruth's basic principles. According to Caruth, the events that traumatize people are often so intense that they cannot be fully understood or unpacked at the moment they occur. Mor's inability to understand the violence which was inflicted upon her brothers signifies the fact that it was incomprehensible.

The mental image of the gunmen as "two orbs of light, orbs like spirits" shows the disconnection from reality and the delayed processing of the trauma. This delayed processing is further demonstrated by Mor's revisiting of the event years afterward, which indicates that the full impact of the trauma is still unknown (Kochai, 2022, p. 89).

According to Caruth, traumatic memories are frequently scattered and alienated from the being's cognition. Mor's visualizing only the gunmen's image but, not the act of murder itself, is a sign of dissociation. The mind's selective memory is used as a defense for the purpose of shielding itself from the full impact of the trauma. These disconnections and segregation are the causes of the lasting impacts of the trauma, as Mor struggles between the reality and the memory.

Caruth highlights the delayed trauma in that the full impact of the traumatic event may not be immediately known but comes to be known later. The traumatic event in her past through her distorted and fragmented memory in her old age demonstrates the idea of belated trauma. With time the traumatic memories may become more blurred or distorted making it difficult for the individuals to accept their past. Mor's memory, which changes gradually, is a symbol of the perpetual influence of the past on her life, and it reflects her continuous attempt to reconcile the past with the present.

CONCLUSION

The chosen stories, though, brilliantly illustrate a multitude of traumas that penetrate the characters in different ways and make their identities and roads to healing. War trauma turns to be a leading topic, which is present everywhere in the stories and shows its deep and long-lasting consequences for the individuals, their families and communities. Not only do the stories present the psychological and emotional harms of war through creative imagery and moving narratives, but they also show the complexity of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), survivor's guilt, and the difficulty of healing in the midst of war's destruction.

The pain of loss and grief is also described with the same intensity, which crosses the cultural and geographical barriers and makes the readers identify with the story on a personal level. The stories take us into the deep and debilitating despair and pain that is caused by the death or absence of loved ones. They help us understand how these experiences alter relationships, perception, and worldview. It could be brought about by the loss of family members or observed through the eyes of medical workers such as Amina, the traumatic experience of loss leaves deep marks that reshape the lives of individuals.

Cultural and generational trauma are the main issues, which are illustrated by the effect of war on the Afghan society and its people down the generations. The novels explore this aspect of trauma through the characters of Yusuf, Amina, and Rangeena who individually and collectively represent the cultural fabric of the nation and how trauma is not only a personal experience but also a collective one, passed down through generations. The stories sensitively illustrate how a trauma is not limited to individual experiences, it has an impact on family bonds, national norms, and the general national identity.

The visualization of the physical trauma is so graphic, thus symbolizing the stark reality of the lives of those who live in the war-torn areas. Whether it is the health problems of characters like Rangeena, which are likely to be long-term, or the immediate

effects of bombings and explosions described in the stories, the stories point to the consequences of war, which the people continue to experience even after the violence has ended.

In the stories the psychological and emotional trauma is shown in the form of complex relationships between the characters and their inner conflicts. From the crumbling conversations between Yusuf and his son's body parts that had been broken into pieces to Rangeena's mental battles with her traumatic past, the stories suddenly penetrate the deep emotional scars left by war, loss, and the effort to hold the family together at the time of unbearable adversities. The use of vivid imagery and compelling narration enables the stories to convey the subtleties of trauma and the indomitability of the human spirit in the face of the extreme sufferings.

The examination of various stories through Cathy Caruth's trauma theory lens gives clear understanding of the enduring effects of war on individual and community life. In each of the stories examined whether it is *Return to Sender or Enough!* Psychic, memory, the stories plot lines reflect the complexity of trauma and the far-reaching consequences it may bring.

The perception of trauma put forward by Caruth about the unclaimed experience that is shown by its delay and incompleteness is one that can be felt in the narratives being studied. In the movie *Return to Sender* the idea of trauma is communicated in a more subtle way by the use of surreal imagery and shocking revelations, which is exactly the point that trauma is a thing which cannot be represented directly as Caruth says. Much like a temporary matter, the characters are also affected by the emotional consequences of loss, leading to estrangement.

Moreover, the traumatic witnessing phenomenon described by Caruth is also visible here as the characters are trying to deal with the complexity of being the witnesses to their own and others' suffering. *Enough!* the narratives illustrate the complexity of the process of testifying and the long way of struggling and coming to terms with the most profound loss.

This research therefore reveals that the battle-related traumas continue to affect people and communities in different ways through a variety of stories. This study, through using Caruth's theory of traumatic experience as an instrument for the analysis, provides a unique perspective on the complexities of trauma and its enduring effects on the human mind, which highlights the significance of the narrative reconstruction and collective witnessing to the process of healing and reconciliation.

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